

Selective Determination of Inorganic and Organic Mercurials in Water by Coldvapour Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometry

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Manuscript received 28 April 1997, revised 28 July 1997, accepted 27 October 1997

The most popular method for the determination of mercury is coldvapour atomic absorption technique. Considerable work is reported on the determination of mercury in solution by flameless coldvapour atomic absorption technique¹. In these methods organomercurials are converted to inorganic form by acid digestion² or uv irradiation³ prior to the determination. To enhance the sensitivity of the technique, preconcentration of mercury in natural waters by dithizone extraction⁴ and reduction aeration techniques⁵ prior to coldvapour atomic absorption spectrophotometric analysis have been reported.

Inorganic and organomercurials can be quantitatively collected on activated charcoal⁶. Magos⁷ reported selective release of inorganic and organomercurials in biological samples. Here we report a method of selective determination of inorganic and organomercurials in water by coldvapour atomic absorption spectrophotometry.

Results and Discussion

The recovery of mercury adsorbed on activated charcoal was studied by adding known quantities of mercuric chloride, methyl mercuric chloride and phenylmercuric chloride to 1 dm³ aliquots of distilled water and acidified with sulphuric acid and left for one day before the analysis. Determinations were carried out with tin(II) chloride alone and tin(II) chloride-cysteine-cadmium chloride mixture.

TABLE 1—RECOVERY OF MERCURY ADSORBED ON ACTIVATED CHARCOAL WITH TIN(II) CHLORIDE AS RELEASING AGENT

Sl. no.	Hg added μg	Hg found μg	Recovery %	Std. dev.
(A) Mercuric chloride :				
1.	40.0	39.6	99.0	0.19
2.	60.0	59.2	98.7	0.21
3.	80.0	79.4	99.3	0.18
4.	100.0	99.0	99.0	0.20
5.	120.0	118.4	98.7	0.23
6.	140.0	138.3	98.8	0.20
7.	160.0	156.8	98.0	0.19
8.	180.0	178.4	99.1	0.21
9.	200.0	198.0	99.0	0.18
(B) Methylmercuric chloride :				
10.	40.0	0	0	0
11.	80.0	0	0	0
12.	120.0	0	0	0
(C) Phenylmercuric chloride :				
13.	40.0	0	0	0
14.	80.0	0	0	0
15.	120.0	0	0	0

TABLE 2—RECOVERY OF MERCURY ADSORBED ON ACTIVATED CHARCOAL WITH TIN(II) CHLORIDE-CADMIUM CHLORIDE MIXTURE AS RELEASING AGENT IN PRESENCE OF CYSTEINE

Sl. no.	Hg added μg	Hg found μg	Recovery %	Std. dev.
(A) Mercuric chloride :				
1.	40.0	39.4	98.5	0.20
2.	60.0	59.6	99.3	0.19
3.	90.0	79.6	99.5	0.19
4.	100.0	98.7	98.7	0.21
5.	120.0	118.6	98.8	0.20
6.	140.0	138.5	99.0	0.17
7.	160.0	157.4	98.4	0.19
(B) Methylmercuric chloride :				
1.	40.0	39.3	98.3	0.22
2.	60.0	59.2	98.7	0.18
3.	80.0	78.4	98.0	0.19
4.	100.0	98.4	98.4	0.20
5.	120.0	118.2	98.5	0.19
6.	140.0	138.0	98.6	0.22
7.	160.0	156.6	97.9	0.21
(C) Phenylmercuric chloride :				
1.	40.0	39.0	97.5	0.18
2.	60.0	58.0	98.0	0.21
3.	80.0	78.2	97.8	0.20
4.	100.0	98.2	98.2	0.19
5.	120.0	117.8	98.2	0.22
6.	140.0	137.0	97.9	0.17
7.	160.0	157.0	98.1	0.19

The results (Table 1) show that tin(II) chloride alone released only inorganic form of mercury adsorbed on activated charcoal and no organic mercury was released. The results (Table 2) also demonstrate that the release of mercury from organomercurials adsorbed on activated charcoal is identical to that of inorganic mercury when cysteine-cadmium chloride is added in addition to tin(II) chloride. These results further show that by employing tin(II) chloride-cysteine-cadmium chloride mixture, total mercury present in sample can be determined. The difference between the mercury determined with cysteine-cadmium chloride and without cysteine-cadmium chloride will give the amount of organic form of mercury present in the sample. Further, the results demonstrate that both inorganic and organic mercury in water up to 40 μg dm⁻³ can be selectively determined.

Experimental

Mercury was determined using a Ecil MA 5800 A analyzer. Mercury solutions (0.1 μg Hg/ml) were prepared

by diluting standard aqueous solutions (100 µg/ml) of mercury(II) chloride, methylmercury(II) chloride and phenylmercury(II) chloride. Tin(II) chloride-cadmium chloride reagent was prepared by heating a mixture of tin(II) chloride (50 g), cadmium chloride (10 g) and conc. HCl (20 ml) to boiling and the volume made up to 100 ml with distilled water after cooling. Solutions of 45% (w/v) NaOH and 10% (w/v) NaCl were prepared in deionized double-distilled water. Granular (particle size 0.5–0.75 mm) activated charcoal chromatographic-quality (Merck) was purified by heating it at 950–1000° in a stream of nitrogen for 30–60 min.

Determination of inorganic mercury : Filtered water sample (1 dm³) was passed through the column containing activated charcoal (1 g) with a flow rate of 4 ml min⁻¹. The activated charcoal with adsorbed mercury was then transferred to the reaction vessel of the coldvapour atomic absorption spectrophotometer. To the charcoal, 16 N H₂SO₄ (5 ml) was added followed by tin(II) chloride (50 mg) and stirred for 5 min. Then 45% NaOH (5 ml) was added and the mercury vapour passed through the absorption cell and its absorption measured. A blank correction was made for each reading.

Determination of total mercury : Acidified and filtered water sample (1 dm³) was passed through the activated charcoal column and the charcoal transferred into the reaction vessel of coldvapour atomic absorption spectrometer. To it, 5% cysteine solution (1 ml) and 16 N H₂SO₄ (5 ml) were added followed by tin(II) chloride-cadmium chloride

solution (1 ml). The mixture was stirred for 5 min, then 45% NaOH (5 ml) added, and its absorbance measured as above.

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